

A Study of Complex Compounds of N-Benzenesulphonyl Glycine with some Metal Ions. Part IX. Effect of Metal Ions on Optical Activity of the Ligand N-Benzenesulphonyl *l*-Glutamic Acid

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The effect due to chelation as well as *pH*-variation on the optical activity of the optically active ligand N-Benzenesulphonyl *l*-glutamic acid has been studied. The changes in optical rotation values are observed on *pH*-variation and on adding Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) salt solutions and a discussion has been made.

In our previous communications^{1,2}, the formation of metal chelates of N-Benzenesulphonyl *l*-glutamic acid (RH₃) in solution and isolation of some of them have been reported. The present paper constitutes the effect on optical activity of the optically active ligand RH₃ due to chelation as well as on *pH* variation. A study of the effect of added acid or alkali on the rotation of amino acids has been made by Wood³. Following similar procedure optical rotation of RH₃ has been determined at different *pH*-values. With a view to observing any relation between optical rotation of RH₃ and structure of chelates, the effect of metal ions—Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II)—on the optical rotation due to the ligand RH₃ at various *pH* values has been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

The naturally occurring *l*-glutamic acid is dextrorotatory, $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ being +31.4°. In the case of monopotassium salt (KRH₂) $[\alpha]_D^{28}$ was found to be +4.39°.

Fig. 1

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A standard solution of RH_3 was prepared by dissolving 9.1155 g of monopotassium salt (KRH_2) in water and the volume was made up to 100 ml. Aliquots of 10 ml were taken in six 50 ml measuring flasks and increasing amounts of KOH solutions were added. Thus solutions were prepared having the same strength with respect to RH_3 , but differing in pH values. Optical rotation of sodium-light due to these solutions were recorded by an electronic polarimeter using a cell of 2.5 cm at room temperature 28–29°. Data are presented graphically (Fig. 1).

To study the effect of metal ions on the optical rotation, solutions of RH_3 were prepared as already stated but before the volume being made up, 5.7 ml of 0.2459 M $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ or 3.4 ml of 0.4112 M $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ or 4.75 ml of 0.2947 M $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solutions were added to obtain solutions having metal ligand ratio 1 : 2. Optical rotation values and pH -values of the solutions were measured. Specific rotation, $[\alpha]_D$ was calculated in each case and was plotted against the corresponding pH (Fig. 1).

DISCUSSION

To study the effect of added alkali on the optical rotation of the ligand (RH_3), monopotassium salt (KRH_2) was taken. The initial minimum value was due to KRH_2 . On further addition of KOH, the value rises to a maximum one at the ratio 1 : 2. Obviously this is due to the formation of K_2RH . On addition of alkali in the ratio 1 : 2.5 the rotation value falls to zero. This is due to the formation of a still newer species probably involving the imido group.

It is believed that the rotation values of optically active ligands change on addition of metal ions provided there is complexation in the solution. Thus the rotation-value of *l*-propylenediamine does not change on addition of $\text{Ba}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{II})$ which obviates that no complex formation takes place⁴. The change in rotation values of RH_3 on adding $\text{Zn}(\text{II})$, $\text{Cd}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ ions shows that complex formation has occurred.

Regarding $\text{Zn}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Cd}(\text{II})$, the observed rotation-values are very nearly the same indicating that the $\text{Zn}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Cd}(\text{II})$ complexes may have analogous structures—probably tetrahedral, $\text{M}(\text{RH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$. For $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$, the rotation values may be considered to be due to the nonlability⁵ of the complexes having tetrahedral configuration. But such complexes of $\text{Zn}(\text{II})$, $\text{Cd}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ are known to be labile. However, the changes in rotation of optically active ligands on complexation may be ascribed simply to environmental effects⁶ as a result of coordination process. Thus in the case of amino acids, as Wood³ has suggested, the breaks in rotation values against pH , correspond to the new species i.e., salts formed in the solution. Similar conclusion may also be made in the formation of complexes.

Thanks are due to Dr. S. C. Pakrashi of Indian Institute of Experimental Medicine, Calcutta for kindly allowing to use the electronic polarimeter.

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Received February 2, 1970

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